

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF CHILDREN'S POETRY IN LITERACY TEACHING

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Abstract. *The article examines the importance and peculiarities of alphabet poems in teaching literacy to children.*

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Children's literature is important not only as a means of education, but also from the point of view of educational literacy, especially in the reading of children of preschool and junior school age, special importance is attached to teaching literacy. We know that children's reading has been studied in three main stages, which are

- 1) reading of children of preschool age from 2 to 6-7 years old
- 2) reading of children of junior school age from 7 to 11-12 years old
- 3) 12-13 to 16-17-year-olds make up the reading of teenagers.

Poems in the alphabet series are practical and theoretical in the first two stages. Munis's treatise "Savodi telim" created in the 19th century is considered one of the first researches on the rules of beautiful writing, addressed to children who are eager to learn calligraphy. Initially, the poems of the literacy series were intended for readers of all ages, but at the beginning of the 20th century, they began to be written specifically for young readers.

Because it is not a secret to anyone that it is necessary to start from the youth to end the lack of enlightenment. In the examples of children's poetry of the 1930s, the ideas of teaching letters and enjoying the light of knowledge were put forward.

The main part of Munis's treatise "Sawadi Talim" is devoted to husnikhat education, and in the part devoted to each letter of the Arabic alphabet, the name of this letter and its characteristic signs are mentioned.

“Зо” уч нуқтау, лек саркаш, [1.Б.24-24]

Қилса бўлур ани қушга ўхшаш.

“Шин” мадини етти нуқта бил,биғ,

Аммо каж эрур биайниҳи тиғ...

The poet takes the point as a criterion for measuring and determining the length of each letter. Simile shows the artistic art in a way typical of children's thinking (zo-qush, shin-tig is likened).

In the children's literature of the 20th century, the first sample of alphabetic poems was created by Sultan Jora under the name "Parade of Letters", and the poem reflects the transition from Latin script to Krill script and its importance.

The complete version of the alphabet poems belongs to the pen of Sh. Sadulla and is called "Alifbe". Quddus Muhammai's "Letter Game" and Adham Rahmat's "Alifbe" are also important in teaching literacy to children.

"Alifbe" alphabet by Sh. Sadulla is designed to teach literacy to children who have just entered school.

Баҳор келди, гул келди, [2.Б.26]

Боғларга булбул келди

We know that the poem is about the letter "B" from the alliteration of sounds. In the verses dedicated to each letter, words that come with the beginning of this letter are given, which creates alliteration of sounds. Along with learning a letter, a young reader learns its pronunciation and words related to that letter. In terms of form, the poem dedicated to each letter consists of two verses, one stanza, expressed in a masnavi style and rhymed with each other.

The poet used poetic arts such as similes and animating in accordance with the thinking and worldview of children, as well as the images of the animal and plant world. The fact that the poem is expressed stanza by stanza does not make it difficult for children to memorize and remember the poem. The poem dedicated to each letter is given in alphabetical order, forming its compositional construction.

By the second half of the 20th century, we see a special appearance of alphabet poems in the work of Tursunboy Adashboev. His poems "Adventure of Letters", "The Riddle Alphabet" are examples of this. "The Adventure of Letters" is a fairy tale-poem, in which the lazy, playful Sabir has a wonderful adventure of searching for thirty-five letters, which brought tears to his eyes, from the alphabet book. The poet skillfully used the art of revitalization and expressed it in stanzas, each stanza consisting of four lines.

As the poem is expressed in a realistic way, each letter starts with the cities that were lost, and the names of the children who go out to find them. With this playful poem, children will learn words and learn to write names and place names.

Баҳром, Баҳри, Баҳодир [3.Б.79]

Белни боғлаб чопишди.

“Б”ни бўлса ўша куни

Бухородан топишди.

Phrases such as "Gird the waist", "Aro kirmoq (used in the meaning of entering the soul)" also begin with this letter, while the words are simple, typical of the thinking of preschool and school-aged children. Another important aspect is that we learn at the end of the play that the incident happened in Sabir's dream, which makes the play livelier. It is also important from a didactic point of view, that is, the negative vices characteristic of children were reflected in the image of Sabir - he brought the child himself to the field. The poet was able to inculcate didactic and educational ideas in this poem, and its presentation in the form of an adventure served to increase children's interest.

Dilshad Rajab's alphabet-poem "Alifbo: Read, Memorize, Write, Paint, Child" creates a whole picture through the images of the world of animals, insects, and plants and invites children to become literate. The stanzas of the poet's poems are weighty, each stanza consists of six or eight verses, and each stanza reflects a separate reality.

Чигиртка зўр чалғувчи, [4.Б.28]

Чалар куй чарчамасдан.

Чирилдоқлар жўр бўлиб

Чириллар ҳар тарафдан.

Чир айланиб ўйнайди

Чиройли капалаклар,

Чапак чалиб қувнайди

Чамандаги чечаклар.

The image of the locust was given by means of a vivid image of its characteristic life situation - the chirping of locusts, smallpox and butterflies in the grass. It is also important to note that more than ten words related to each letter are given as examples. There are twelve words in the paragraph above about the letter "Ch". These children increase their vocabulary and develop their speech. If you pay attention, no letter name is mentioned in any clause, you will find out which letter is being talked about from the words related to it. Each paragraph expresses a mutual reality, has a thematic composition, that is, the beginning, the development of thoughts, and the end.

Alphabet poems are not limited to teaching a child to read and write, but are works of art that expand his world view and increase his aesthetic taste, and each poet approaches and expresses from a different angle. Through poems, our children learn the alphabet quickly and easily, and in other forms of poems, through word games, they learn to form words and distinguish their meanings.

In Tursunboy Adashboev's poem "The difference is in one letter", a new word is formed by removing letters, which is almost like a game method, which increases the vocabulary of the young reader.

“Бол” деганда тамшангайсиз чорасиз, [5.Б.101]

Битта ҳарфдан камайтириб борасиз.

“Ол” сўзини эшитганда мезбондан,

Сўнг асалдан нонга суртиб оласиз.

“О” ҳарфини алмаштирсак “Ё” билан,

Тулпор-тойга у елпиғич “Ёл” бўлар,

“Т” тиркалса соя-салқин “Тол” бўлар,

“Ч”ни қўшсак тўқсон ёшли “Чол” бўлар.

Алмаштирсак агар “Д”ни тўсатдан,

Тўқсон ёшли бобом қадди “Дол” бўлар.

Тўғри келса, “Х” ҳарфини қўллашга,

Холиданинг ёноғида “Ҳол” бўлар.

The poem is expressed in a playful way, in which children act together with the poet, create new words by adding and replacing letters, distinguishing the structure and meaning of the word. By replacing a single initial letter, several words with different meanings are formed.

A new word can be created not only by replacing letters in a poem, but also by removing one of them. This poem is also a word-building game and riddle poem, which helps children to increase their vocabulary, avoid spelling mistakes, and strengthen their minds. The poet gives seven riddles, but the number of words given is eight, perhaps this is also a riddle for clever children.

Using the poetic method in learning and teaching the alphabet is convenient and effective, and it helps to quickly develop literacy. "Alphabet" and word game poems occupy a special place in children's literature and are important for the educational and spiritual development of the young generation. The poems based on word games help to develop the child's thinking and memory while forming words, distinguishing them from a spiritual point of view, and increasing vocabulary. Shows wealth, possibilities, ways of word formation. Increases attention and caution

to the language and use of words in the young generation, helps to avoid spelling mistakes in writing.

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